

THE USAGE OF ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF DEMENTIA: ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Farrux Majlimov¹

Madina Umarova²

Avazbek Koraboyev³

Yorqin Sattarov⁴

Tashkent Medical Academy

KEYWORDS

Dementia, Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Beta-amyloid plaques, Neurofibrillary tangles, Electroencephalography (EEG), Neural biomarkers, EEG frequency bands, Delta frequency, Theta frequency, Alpha frequency, Beta frequency, Gamma frequency, Tau protein

ABSTRACT

Dementia is a condition characterized by progressive or persistent loss of mechanical functioning, impairment of abstract thinking, and memory, and abrupt changes in behavior and attitude. While dementia is a general term for different diseases, Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a specific type of them. AD development is mostly associated with beta-amyloid plaques, which develop among neurons, and neurofibrillary tangles developing inside them. There is evidence that dementia associated with AD will cause changes in electrical activity in the brain, voltage potential across the membranes of axons. Electroencephalography (EEG) is a diagnosing method that measures the electrical activity in the brain. In this article the deployment of EEG in the AD's diagnosis will be discussed.

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DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.14543530**

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¹ Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

² Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

³ Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

⁴ Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Introduction.

In 2023, the average world life expectancy has reached 73.16 years which is 0.24% more than that in 2022. As this number continues to grow, the likelihood of elderly people developing AD – a progressive loss of memory, thinking, and decision-making abilities that disturb the ability to carry out everyday activities – increases substantially. AD is the major cause of dementia, accounting for 60-80% of all cases, and it presents significant economic and health concerns. Pathologically, AD is essentially defined by the formation of amyloid-beta plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, which are linked to synapse loss and cortical volume decrease. Memory impairment is one of the early clinical symptoms, and it gradually spreads to other cognitive domains. However, research indicates that pathophysiological alterations occur decades before clinical symptoms arise, confounding efforts to prevent or delay disease progression. Furthermore, current early indicators such as amyloid-beta levels are not significantly predictive of cognitive function, challenging the assessment of cognitive decline. This emphasizes the importance of estimating cognitively relevant neural function in the early stages of the disease in order to provide prognostic markers of AD progression and guide therapeutic interventions before irreversible neurophysiological and cognitive damage occurs. EEG is a tool that has shown a potential for identifying the early-stage biomarkers of AD. It records the electrical activity of the brain generated by postsynaptic currents which is synchronous among many neurons. As a candidate for identifying early biomarkers of different neurological disorders. EEG has few advantages over other new technologies. For example, it is non-invasive, widely available in worldwide healthcare systems, portable and cost-effective than other neuroimaging methods such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and positron emission tomography (PET).

Main body.

EEG recording can be taken in several different ways and neurophysiologists will explain the procedure to the patients. Before the procedure the scalp of the patients will be cleaned, then the small sensors will be attached to pick up signals in the brain. There are various types of EEG: routine EEG, sleep or sleep-deprived EEG, ambulatory EEG, video telemetry.

Routine EEG lasts 20-40 minutes. Doctors may ask patients to open or close their eyes and breathe in and out. Sometimes, flashlight is used to check if it affects the activity of the brain. While sleep EEG is recorded during a patient's sleep, sleep-deprived EEG requires the patient to stay awake all night. Ambulatory EEG is attached to the scalp of the patient, the patient can perform normal daily activities while EEG records brain's electrical activity day and night over one or more days. There is rising evidence that particular EEG signatures are linked to Alzheimer's disease. The most consistent finding comes from spectral analysis, which breaks down the EEG signal into its constituent frequency bands: delta (1-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-12 Hz), beta (15-30 Hz), and gamma (30-90 Hz). Many studies have shown a slowing of the EEG signal, characterized by power increases in lower frequencies (delta and theta) and decreases in higher frequencies (alpha and beta), along with a reduction of the peak alpha frequency, in AD patients compared to healthy controls (HC). These signal calculations also showed the association of type-2 diabetes - mellitus and mild cognitive impairment with the high risk of AD development. Explanation for changes in postsynaptic currents is connected with the pathology of the tau protein. Tau may accumulate in the postsynaptic area and some studies have shown that phosphorylated tau (one of the causes of AD development) may be found in dendrites of neurons, affecting synaptic transportation. In some research experiments the mislocalized tau caused the reduction of excitatory postsynaptic currents in rats. Therefore, EEG is one of the promising methods for early diagnosis of cognitive biomarkers of AD.

Conclusion.

As the number of elderly people is increasing worldwide, many cognitive health problems will arise, especially those related to dementia. AD is one of the most widespread neurodegenerative diseases. This emphasizes the importance of improving diagnostic tools utilized by specialists. It helps with early diagnosis, better treatment and good results. As it was said in the article, EEG may be the potential candidate for detecting the early signs of ad and many other cognitive dysfunctions through non-invasive approach.

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